

Paper 9

INNOVATIONS AS A KEY TO SUCCESS IN MODERN BANKING

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Abstract:

Banking sector welcomes large scope for innovations in terms process, marketing and relationship management. To gain competitive advantage over the competing banks, a bank can survive and sustain with innovative way of processing, approaching and managing. Open banking, phygitive delivery, block chains, robot advising, payments anywhere, mobile and internet banking and other more innovations in the banking sector help the banks to achieve success. This paper aims to observe the needs, types, and ways of innovations in the path of a bank's success

Keywords: Relationship managements, competitive advantage, block chain, robot advising, payments anywhere, phygitive delivery.

Motive: Increased commitment to innovation in response to consumer expectations is one of the primary findings of the [10th annual Innovation in Retail Banking report](#)

Introduction:

Innovation is a key to success in every sectors of economy. Being a prominent economic player, the banking sector welcomes innovations too. They are no longer restricted to traditional methods. Thus, to increase the business opportunities and capture the fresh market banks are resorting to innovation. Banks are already heading towards Industry 4.0 (Automation trend), creating a bank of future, enhancing financial inclusion and facilitating the convenient and digital experience for its customers worldwide.

As part of the industry 4.0, banks are experimenting with new mobile applications and voice-enabled gadgets to enhance both delivery and customization. As technologies continue to evolve, the banking sector will continue to accelerate its investments in innovation and digital enhancements.

Major innovations in banking which have been a key to success in modern banking operations in this digitech era are as follows.

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1. Expansion of Open Banking through APIs.

The regulatory bodies globally are requiring banks to enable customers to share their data securely with third parties to experience new financial services and increase competition in

the banking industry. Through Applications Programming Interfaces consumers have greater freedom and control over their banking operations

Open banking APIs accelerate innovation and collaboration, leading to expanded banking ecosystems that could include more than just financial services to make a consumer's lifestyle better.

2. Commitment to Physical and Digital Delivery

The banking companies are introducing digital only banking entities, as a lot of transactions are moving to digital channels and also to combat the high cost of a traditional branch network costs. By digital-only banking system for collecting deposits, to using digital platforms for lending, investing and speciality services, banks and financial firms are focusing on quality customer experiences and increased value for customers with these phygitive delivery systems.

3. Cardless ATM service

For the first time in the globe, BankDhofar in Oman has launched a cardless banking service for ATMs which allows customers to carry out ATM transactions easily by using only their mobile numbers. For this service, customers need to activate their mobile number through the BankDhofar call centre or their mobile banking app. Once verified, customers can go to the nearest BankDhofar ATM and insert their mobile number, one-time PIN (OTP) and the card PIN, and carry out their transaction. Cardless banking allows customers to withdraw cash, pay bills, request for cheque book, make balance inquiry, and request for a mini statement.

4. Predictive Banking

One of the most exciting innovations in 2019 is predictive banking. For the first time, the banking industry is consolidating all internal and external data and building predictive profiles of customers in real time. With rich, accurate and financially viable consumer data, financial institutions know their customers very well and are able to offer advice for the future, while increasing security and efficiency. With robo-advisors financial institutions offer 'next-best actions' with personalised solutions in real time and universal cash management solutions that address implicit needs in an integrated service. Information with figures and insights are contextually delivered with the aim of proactively changing customer's behavioural patterns.

5. Block chain

This works by using a network of computers, all of which must approve a transaction in a chain of computer code. Details of the transfer are then recorded on a public ledger for anyone on the network to see. It has huge potential for banking, where it could be used to improve the security of financial transactions, decentralized services and improve speed to market for new products. There is no shortage of use-cases and applications for block chain currently being explored by the finance community. It can be used to securely store client identities or handle cross-border payments. It could even lead to 'smart contracts' that complete trades and deals automatically. A report from Santander InnoVentures

suggests that block chain technologies could save banks as much as \$20 billion in infrastructure costs by 2022.

CONCLUSION: This paper describes the innovations and types of innovations that enable the banking sector to gear its operations for the better customer experiences and enhancement of relationships as a competitive advantage to attain success in this digitech era.

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